

IMPLANT-PROSTHETIC REHABILITATION OF THE ATROPHIC POSTERIOR MAXILLA USING “PARA-SINUSAL” IMPLANTS: A CASE SERIES

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ABSTRACT

Objective: The rehabilitation of the atrophic posterior maxilla is one of the most complex challenges in implantology, given the reduced amount of available bone due to secondary pneumatization of the maxillary sinus and crestal resorption. Depending on the case, both Major Sinus Lift and zygomatic implants are definitive and consolidated solutions, but often invasive and not without possible complications. The objective of this case series is to illustrate a method for partial and, in some cases, full-arch rehabilitation of the atrophic posterior maxilla, through the insertion of implants defined as “para-sinusual”. This protocol, which involves the use of tilted implants positioned parallel to the palatal vault, offers in both situations a decidedly minimally invasive therapeutic alternative with benefits in terms of both time and overall costs for the realization of both partial and full-arch rehabilitations.

Materials and Methods: The study included patients with residual bone height less than 5 mm, where maxillary sinus pneumatization prevented the insertion of conventional axial implants without resorting to “sinus lift” techniques. Tilted implants with anchorage in the palatal bone portion of the

maxilla were used, thus allowing sufficient primary support for immediate stability. The surgical protocol involves the use of guided templates for optimal precision in implant placement and immediate prosthetic management to ensure functionality. **Results:** During the follow-up period, no implants were lost and patients showed optimal healing without signs of complications. No post-operative infections, nor evidence of peri-implantitis or pathological bone resorption were found. **Conclusion:** The para-sinus implant technique represents an innovation in the management of posterior maxillary atrophy, reducing the need for complex and invasive surgical procedures. Within the limitations of this study, the results obtained suggest that this method may represent an effective therapeutic option for the implant-prosthetic rehabilitation of patients with severe bone atrophy.

INTRODUCTION

Edentulism of the upper jaw leads to progressive bone resorption, which manifests as a reduction in crestal height and pneumatization of the maxillary sinus. This process, associated with the evident need to reduce the distal cantilever as much as possible in prosthetics, imposes choices aimed at making the emergence point of the distal abutment in the arch as posterior as possible,^[1] making the placement of conventional implants difficult and requiring advanced surgical solutions to achieve functional and aesthetic rehabilitation. Traditionally, Major Sinus Lift has been considered the technique of choice to increase the available bone volume in the atrophic maxilla, allowing the placement of standard implants.^[2,3] However, this procedure presents some criticalities, including a high complication rate, a long healing period, and the need to manage any post-graft resorption. An alternative, especially indicated in cases of full-arch rehabilitation of the atrophic patient, is represented by zygomatic implants^[4,5] which exploit the extramaxillary anchorage of the zygomatic bone to bypass posterior maxillary atrophy. This technique, although effective, is also complex and requires adequate surgical experience, as well as a surgical procedure managed under general anesthesia or at least deep sedation, therefore strictly in a hospital setting.

With the aim of reducing the need for zygomatic implants and avoiding “bone grafting” techniques,^[6,7] the use of “trans-crestal” implants^[8] and “trans-sinus” implants^[9] has been successfully described in selected cases where predisposing conditions existed. In this context, “para-sinus” implants, when applicable, can represent a further innovative, absolutely minimally invasive solution, with enormous savings in time and resources, to be combined with the now standard techniques of using Tilted Implants.^[10,11,12,13,14,15,16,17,18]

This technique involves the insertion of implants with an inclination that follows the available bone conformation, anchoring, when volumetrically suitable, in the palatal portion of the maxilla without therefore the need for sinus floor elevation (Fig. 1). The implant biomechanics of this configuration and the manufacturing material in Grade V Titanium alloy (Al6V4) allow for optimal resistance to masticatory forces, minimizing the risk of permanent deformation or even fracture of the fixture and primary prosthetic components that will constantly work at least at 17° of inclination even for single elements, while offering a correct discharge of masticatory forces in the area of maximum occlusal load (1st premolar - 2nd upper molar).

(Fig. 1)

The objective of this study is to present the results of a case series treated with implants therefore defined by us as “para-sinusal”, evaluating the predictability of the method and comparing its results with traditional techniques.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Patient Selection

Patients included in this study presented with residual bone height less than 4 mm in the posterior maxilla, with a degree of secondary sinus pneumatization such that it prevented the insertion of standard axial implants.

To date, 10 patients in total have been selected, but for this analysis, only the 4 patients with a follow-up greater than or equal to 36 months have been presented.

Implants Used

For this study, the Paltop PCA implant was chosen, characterized by a macro-morphology that optimizes its adaptability to critical bone conditions, a highly consolidated surface micro-

morphology for efficacy (Sandblasted Double etched), and excellent surface cleaning technology (K-Learn™ - UPW) which guarantees against the risk of lot-failure related to surface contaminants as well demonstrated by XPS analysis. Last, but not least, its manufacture in Grade V Titanium ensures both a level of osseointegration absolutely comparable to that of pure Grade IV Titanium and a high mechanical resistance with a Yield Strength of 850MPa Vs 480MPa for Grade IV. This allows for the safe insertion of implants with inclinations of 17° and 30°, including smaller diameters (3.75 mm and 3.25 mm), even when used singly or in small partials.^[19,20,21,22,23,24,25,26,27]

Criteria

a/ Number and Age Range

Selection of at least 10 patients, male or female, who have passed cessation of growth. No upper limit of age.

b/ Inclusion Criteria

- The subject must be in such a physical and mental condition that a 3-year follow-up period can be carried out without problems.
- Stable situation of adjacent teeth.
- The subject must have less than 5mm bone height under the maxillary sinus floor.
- Normal presence of keratinized gingiva.
- Absence of interarch discrepancies.

c/ Exclusion Criteria

- Patient circumstances where the treatment could affect the patient's health or the patient's cooperation.
- Any disorders in the planned implant area such as previous tumors, chronic bone disease or previous irradiation, clinically active periodontal disease, periapical lesions in the neighboring teeth.
- Subjects who have been treated with, or are in need of bone grafts.
- Extraction sockets in the area for implant placement or previous surgery in the area in the 6 months before.
- Heavy smoker (above 10 per day) or alcoholism.
- The subject is not able to give her/his informed consent of participating.
- Bruxism and/or parafunctions.
- Pregnancy.

Surgical-Prosthetic Protocol

A/Preoperative phase

- CBCT evaluation for three-dimensional analysis of the maxilla focused on assessing the thickness and conformation of the paranasal palatal wall in the area of interest.
- Intervention planning with guided surgery software (DTX Implant), and creation of the digital project of the static computerized surgical guide.
- Professional oral hygiene with laser treatment to reduce the pre-operative bacterial load.
- Preparation of the 3D printing file with “Autodesk - MeshMixer” and “Anycubic Photon Workshop” software.
- Printing of the surgical guide with “Anycubic Photon Mono X6K” printer with 200µ layer.

B/Surgical phase

- Verification of the precision of the surgical guide fit.
- Local anesthesia with infiltration of Septanest 40 mg/ml with adrenaline.
- Minimally invasive crestal incision, aimed at the translocation of available keratinized tissue.
- Preparation of the implant site with progressive calibrated drills to obtain optimal primary stability.
- Insertion of tilted Paltop PCA implants with anchorage in the palatal portion of the maxillary bone.
- Immediate application of Multi-Unit abutments for immediate prosthetic management.
- PTFE or resorbable suture for healing as free as possible from inflammation.

C/Postoperative phase

In relation to the “clean” minimally invasive surgery performed, we always opt to avoid antibiotic therapies ([19]).

- Prescription of anti-inflammatory (Seractil 400 mg, 1 tablet every 12 hours x 5 days).
- Weekly checks for the first month, then follow-up at 2, 3, 6 and 12 months.
- Finalization between the 4th and 6th month.

DISCUSSION

Bone atrophy of the upper jaw, often combined with secondary pneumatization of the maxillary sinus, often represents a challenge for the placement of axial implants. Traditional techniques of maxillary sinus lift and bone grafting, although effective and well-established

for methods and surgical techniques, can lead to numerous complications, such as extensive perforation of the Schneiderian membrane, infections, sinusitis, and resorption of the grafted material.^[3]

Para-sinusial implants, when anatomically favorable conditions exist, can offer a valid alternative, providing a relatively simple, economical, immediate loading solution that is absolutely appreciated by the patient given the minimally invasive “Guided Surgery” approach, and this potentially with both now standard static computerized guided surgery techniques and with the more recent navigated computerized guided surgery techniques (Nobel X-Guide; Straumann Falcon, Yomi Neocis).

In particular, if we refer to full-arch restorations, this provides us with an additional tool to reduce the need for zygomatic implants, in addition to the trans-crestal and trans-sinusial placement already described in the literature,^[8,9] implants which, although a strategic option for severe atrophy, are to be considered decidedly advanced surgery requiring very high surgical skills from the operator and surgical staff, being harbingers of possible significant intraoperative complications, such as perforation of the orbit or injury to the infraorbital nerve, as well as possible postoperative complications such as infections, mucosal dehiscences, reactive epulides, up to oro-antral communication. Para-sinusial implants therefore represent a decidedly minimally invasive and biomechanically reliable solution for the rehabilitation of the atrophic posterior maxilla, reducing the number of Major Sinus Lifts in single or few-implant posterior district restorations as well as the zygomatic implants necessary in full-arch rehabilitations.

CASE 1

A 48-year-old male patient presented with intercalated edentulism at element 2.6. CBCT revealed a bone thickness at the maxillary sinus floor between 3.2 mm and 3.8 mm, but a palatal parasinusial wall thickness suitable for the placement of a 3.75 mm by 13 mm fixture associated with a 17° angled Multi Unit Abutment (**Fig.2, 3**). Four months after immediate loading, the case was finalized. (**Fig.4-10**) Follow-up at 40 months. (**Fig.11**)

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(Fig.11)

CASE 2

A 44-year-old male patient. Immediate post-extraction implant surgery with immediate loading of Q2 was performed, as the patient presented with destructive caries affecting elements 2.4, 2.5, 2.6, and 3.6. (Fig. 12)

3 implants were planned and placed:

- Straight implant 3.25 mm by 16 mm in site 2.4
- Tilted 17° 3.25 mm by 16 mm in site 2.5
- “Para-sinusual” 3.75 mm by 13 mm in site 2.6 (Fig.13-27)

Concurrently, temporary restorations, prepared based on the CAS project (DTX Studio Implant - Meshmixer) and *in house* printed in PMMA (Fig. 28-32), were placed. After 5 months, the case was finalized with a Partial Implant Bridge in ceramic zirconia 1.4–1.6 (Fig. 33-36). Control X-ray at 45 months. (Fig. 37)

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CASE 3

A 56-year-old female patient. Immediate post-extraction implant surgery with immediate loading of Q1.

She presented with focal periodontal damage affecting the root furcation of element 1.6 and the distal root of 1.5, with grade 2 mobility and apical resorption (**Fig.38**).

2 K-PCA 3.75 mm by 13 mm para-sinusal implants were placed in sites 1.5 and 1.6 respectively, both with 17° angled MUA abutments (**Fig.39-41**). Immediate temporization was performed (**Fig.42-51**). Finalization at 6 months (**Fig.52-60**). Follow-up at 38 months. (**Fig.61**)

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CASE 4

A 53-year-old female patient. Complex case with severe deep-bite and bilateral upper molar edentulism (**Fig. 62-63**).

Combined orthodontic and implant-prosthetic treatment was performed.

In Q2, lacking the requirements for the para-sinusal technique, MSL (**Fig. 64**) and Nobelbiocare N1 implants were used.

In Q1, treated with the minimally invasive graft-free para-sinusal technique, the following were placed in static guided surgery (**Fig.70-71**):

- K-PCA 4.2 mm by 11.5 mm in site 1.6
- K-PCA 3.75 mm by 11.5 mm in site 1.7

with 17° angled MUA abutments and immediate temporization. Finalization with ceramic zirconia bridges in Q1 and Q2 (**Fig. 72-76**). Follow-up at 3 years. (**Fig. 77**)

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RESULTS

Clinical analysis showed excellent implant stability, with average ISQ (Ostell) values above 65 already at the first post-operative measurement. No infections, surgical or prosthetic complications were observed. In all treated cases, to date, the implant and prosthetic success rate has been 100%. The subjective patient satisfaction evaluation, both for surgery with temporary restorations and for permanent prosthetics, was 100%. As of the current date, 3 of the 5 patients with a follow-up greater than 18 months have exceeded 3 years from both the date of surgery and permanent prosthetics.

CONCLUSIONS

The implants used, in “*para-sinus*” mode, have proven capable of offering a valid alternative for implant rehabilitation in patients with posterior maxillary atrophy, otherwise candidates for maxillary sinus floor elevation techniques. Their configuration allows for predictable results, reducing the need for bone regeneration procedures and improving patient comfort. Despite the highly positive results, this “case series” has some limitations, including the total number of patients treated and the need for a longer overall follow-up to evaluate the long-term stability of bone profiles on the one hand and implant-prosthetic rehabilitations on the other.

The experimentation therefore continues now in multicenter, in order to collect an adequate case series that allows us to verify in the medium term (5 years) a sufficient number of treated cases for a complete scientific validation of the proposed surgical-prosthetic protocol.

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